

Entry: Checklist for reviewing Zenodo submissions (ENTRY5975)

Properties

General info

Name:

Checklist for reviewing Zenodo submissions Document:

Checklist for reviewing Zenodo submissions

1. Title of Zenodo publication: make sure that terms like data set, raw data, etc. are not used in the title; they can be put in brackets after the title
2. Existence of descriptive keywords
3. Description of Zenodo entry: abstract and potential DOI-link to journal manuscript
4. README-file that explains the purpose, content, format, etc. of the uploaded data files?
5. Uploaded files: Standardized file formats such as TIFF or JPEG have well-documented structures. In contrast, CSV, TXT, XLS don't inherently provide information about how and what data is stored. Hence, every non-standardized file format should contain a header with metadata and data processing instructions (format specification, software, etc.)
6. Avoid the publication of temporary/hidden files or file that were automatically generated by the operating system. E.g. Thumbs.db (Windows), _MACOSX, .git, .svn,
7. Funding (Number 416229255 and link to our website www.crc1411.research.fau.eu):

Additional details

Funding

CRC 1411 - Design of Particulate Products 416229255
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft

See tutorial for Creating a README file and Guideline for Zenodo publications for further details.